

ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY AND HUMAN RESOURCE COMPETENCIES ON TRANSPORTATION MODES AND THEIR IMPACT ON SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY CHAIN DISTRIBUTION: A STUDY AT PT POS INDONESIA (PERSERO)

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ABSTRACT

The rapid development of digital transformation and sustainability demands in the logistics sector are driving companies to strengthen their distribution systems by optimizing transportation modes. PT Pos Indonesia (Persero), as a state-owned enterprise, is required to improve its distribution performance by integrating digital technology and enhancing human resource (HR) competencies. However, challenges still exist in aligning the use of digital technology with existing transportation systems and the varying competencies of human resources. This research aims to analyze the influence of digital technology and human resource competencies on transportation modes, and their impact on sustainable supply chain distribution. The research uses a quantitative approach with a causal-associative method. Data was collected thru a structured questionnaire distributed to 100 respondents from the Operations Division at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero), and analyzed using the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method with the assistance of SMARTPLS 4.0 software. The research results indicate that human resource competence has a positive and significant effect on both transportation mode and sustainable supply chain distribution, while digital technology only has a significant effect on supply chain distribution, but not on transportation mode. Transportation mode was also found to have a significant effect on supply chain sustainability and partially mediate the influence of other variables. Thus, this study concludes that the success of sustainable supply chain distribution is highly influenced by the synergy between human resource competencies and effective transportation modes, while the integration of digital technology still needs to be improved in the context of transportation mode management at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero).

Keywords: Carbon Digital Technology; Human Resource Competencies; Sustainable Supply Chain; Transportation Mode.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and toward Society 5.0, digital transformation has become a primary requirement in the global logistics system. According to a report by the World Economic Forum (2020), over 65% of global logistics companies are adopting digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Big Data to improve distribution speed, cost efficiency, and supply chain transparency. The adoption of digitalization has become the primary solution for overcoming complex logistics challenges, thru transparency, efficiency, and sustainability in the distribution of goods. Digitalization in logistics not only

concerns warehouse management and goods tracking, but also directly influences the selection and management of transportation modes used. Transportation modes supported by digital systems such as real-time GPS-based tracking, AI-powered automated routing, and supply chain data integration enable companies to improve punctuality, reduce operational costs, and lower carbon emissions, thus contributing to the creation of sustainable supply chain distribution.

PT Pos Indonesia (Persero), as the oldest state-owned enterprise in the courier and logistics service sector, plays a strategic role in the national distribution ecosystem. However, the company faces significant challenges in transforming into a modern, technology-based logistics organization. Although PT Pos Indonesia

(Persero) has begun implementing digital systems (such as PosAja and digital tracking), the alignment between digital technology and human resource competencies remains a major obstacle.

A crucial problem arises in the aspect of transportation modes. To date, PT Pos Indonesia (Persero) has only relied on the GPS system for fleet tracking, but its utilization has not been optimal for strategic decision-making, such as selecting the fastest routes, integrating multimodal transportation (land, air, sea), and optimizing capacity and delivery schedules. The development of digitalizing transportation modes, such as AI-based fleet management systems, real-time logistics dashboards, and predictive algorithms, has not been fully implemented. This has resulted in a high rate of delivery delays, which, according to the annual report of PT Pos Indonesia (Persero) (2022), was still above 15% in the first quarter.

The solutions offered in this research emphasize the holistic integration of Green Logistics and digitalization, collaboration with clean energy technology providers, and data-driven efficiency measurement systems. With these steps, PT Pos Indonesia (Persero) can strengthen its competitiveness as a modern, cost-effective, and environmentally conscious national logistics service provider.

Additionally, the impact of the lack of digital transportation mode development also includes unrealized efficiency. Logistics distribution costs are still considered high, especially in remote areas that are not accessible to major infrastructure. Another challenge is the limited human resources available to operate digital systems, as well as the uneven distribution of transportation infrastructure across different regions.

Meanwhile, the development of sustainable supply chain distribution has become a significant focus. A sustainable supply chain not only demands cost efficiency but also prioritizes the triple bottom line principle (Elkington, 2017), which encompasses economic, social, and environmental aspects. PT Pos Indonesia (Persero) is required not only to be fast and affordable in distribution, but also environmentally friendly and socially responsible. This aligns with the principles of Green Logistics advocated by Carter & Rogers (2018), where transportation mode management plays a crucial role in reducing carbon emissions and energy consumption.

Several previous studies have discussed digital transformation in the supply chain (Ivanov et al., 2019; Bag et al., 2021), but there are still few studies that specifically analyze the impact of digital technology on transportation modes (not just supply chain management in general), provide empirical studies in the context of state-owned logistics companies like PT Pos Indonesia (Persero) which face different challenges compared to private companies, and link the impact of digital technology to the sustainability of supply chain distribution, covering economic (efficiency), social (accessibility), and environmental (transport emissions) aspects. Previous studies by Prasetyo & Basuki (2021) have shown that the digitalization of logistics can

significantly improve efficiency if accompanied by adequate and competent human resource support. However, there has been no comprehensive research integrating digital technology and human resource competencies with the development of transportation modes and their impact on sustainable supply chain distribution within the context of state-owned logistics companies like PT Pos Indonesia (Persero).

Therefore, this research is important and relevant to conduct in order to analyze how digital technology and human resource competencies influence transportation modes, and how this impacts sustainable supply chain distribution. The findings of this research are expected to provide a strategic contribution to national logistics digitalization policy-making and serve as an evaluative model for logistics transformation in state-owned enterprises.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Legitimacy Theory

A literature review plays an important role in constructing the research conceptual framework by examining relevant theories and synthesizing previous findings to identify research gaps that can be further investigated. In the context of logistics transformation in state-owned companies like PT Pos Indonesia (Persero), this review focuses on key concepts influencing the selection of transportation modes and their impact on sustainable supply chain distribution. Literature will be classified into several main themes, namely the role of digital technology in logistics decision-making, and the importance of human resource competence in managing efficient transportation systems for the flexibility and effectiveness of transportation modes. In addition, theories and empirical studies related to sustainable supply chain distribution will also be discussed, both from international and national perspectives (e.g., Christopher, 2016; Hapsari & Nugroho, 2022). With this approach, the literature review will provide the theoretical basis and analytical direction for quantitatively testing the relationships between variables and their contribution to the sustainability of the national logistics distribution.

2.2. Definition and Concepts of Digital Technology in Logistics

Digital technology in logistics encompasses the integration of data-driven software and systems to optimize supply chain management and logistics decision-making. According to Westerman et al. (2011), digitalization can improve visibility, speed, and accuracy in transportation planning and goods delivery. Digital Transformation Theory (Bharadwaj et al., 2013) states that the use of big data, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT) plays a significant role in creating a supply chain that is responsive and adaptable to changes in market demand.

2.3. Definition and Concept of Human Resource Competency

Human resource competency refers to the combination of knowledge, skills, and work attitudes necessary to perform tasks effectively and efficiently. Spencer & Spencer (1993) in their

competency model state that competency consists of five main elements: motives, traits, self-concept, knowledge, and skills. In the context of logistics, competent human resources are able to operate the latest technologies, analyze logistics data, and respond dynamically to changes in transportation modes (Gunasekaran et al., 2017).

2.4 Definition and Concepts of Transportation Modes

Modes of transportation are the methods or types of transport used in the process of shipping goods, whether by land, sea, air, or rail. According to Rodrigue et al. (2017), the choice of transportation mode is influenced by cost, delivery time, capacity, and geographical accessibility. Logistics Transportation Theory emphasizes that selecting the right mode can reduce logistics costs, speed up delivery, and support operational sustainability

2.5 Definition and Concept of Sustainable Supply Chain Distribution

Sustainable supply chain distribution refers to a logistics system that is not only economically efficient but also environmentally friendly and socially responsible. Carter & Rogers (2008), within the Triple Bottom Line framework, state that sustainability encompasses economic, environmental, and social aspects. Sustainable distribution practices include using low-emission transportation modes, optimizing delivery routes, and utilizing environmentally friendly technologies that support resource efficiency and reduce carbon footprints.

2.6 Relationship Among Variables and Hypothesis Development

2.6.1 The Impact of Digital Technology on the Efficiency of Transportation Operations

Digital technology is the foundation of modern logistics transportation management through the integration of real-time systems and data that support route planning, fleet control, and data-driven decision-making, thereby improving operational efficiency and reliability (Ivanov et al., 2019; Hui Jing, 2024):

H1: Digital technology has a positive impact on transportation operational efficiency.

2.6.2 The Influence of Human Resources Competence on the Efficiency of Transportation Operations

The successful implementation of digital technology in transportation management is largely determined by human resource competency, as digital literacy and analytical skills are

prerequisites for the effective use of digital transportation systems (Laudon & Laudon, 2018; Prasetyo & Basuki, 2021):

H2: Human resource (HR) competency has a positive effect on transportation operations efficiency.

2.6.3 The Impact of Digital Technology on Sustainable Supply Chain Distribution

Digital technology improves the transparency, efficiency, and reliability of supply chain distribution through cost reductions, increased timeliness, and real-time environmental impact monitoring, significantly impacting supply chain performance and sustainability (Bag et al., 2021; Hui Jing, 2024), hypothesis:

H3: Digital technology has a positive impact on sustainable supply chain distribution.

2.6.4 The Influence of Human Resource Competence on Sustainable Supply Chain Distribution

Human resource competency plays a strategic role in the operational success and sustainability of the supply chain, as human capability is a key factor, alongside technology, in managing business processes responsibly and efficiently (Elkington, 2017; Prasetyo & Basuki, 2021). On this basis, the following hypothesis is advanced:

H4: Human resource (HR) competency has a positive impact on sustainable supply chain distribution.

2.6.5 The Impact of Transportation Operation Efficiency on Sustainable Supply Chain Distribution

Efficient and integrated transportation operations play a crucial role in improving supply chain distribution performance. Increasing the reliability and flexibility of transportation modes has been shown to positively impact supply chain performance, as well as the timeliness and efficiency of distribution (Ivanov et al., 2019; Atieh et al., 2025). Hence, it is hypothesized that:

H5: Efficient transportation operations positively impact sustainable supply chain distribution.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

To analyze this research, a quantitative method with a causal associative approach was used to examine the influence of digital technology and human resource competence on transportation modes and their impact on sustainable supply chain distribution at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero). The conceptual framework of the study is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 3. 1 Research Design

3.3 Population and Sample

Data was collected by distributing questionnaires to 100 respondents selected from a total population of approximately 200 employees working in the Operations Division. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting respondents, with the criteria that they had worked for at least 1 year in a unit directly related to transportation mode management and company digital system development.

3.3 Data Collection

This study used a questionnaire as a data collection technique, namely delivering written questions to respondents (Sugiyono, 2020). The questionnaires were distributed directly to the research respondents.

3.4 Data Sources

The data source used by the author in this study is primary data. According to Sugiyono (2020: 456), primary data is a data source

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the validity and reliability tests indicate that the data is suitable for further analysis. Validity and reliability tests were conducted to ensure that the research instrument can accurately and consistently measure the desired variables. With external loading criteria above 0.7, AVE above 0.5, and composite reliability above 0.7, the questionnaire demonstrates a high level of internal consistency.

that directly provides data to data collectors..

3.5 Data Analysis

The Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method, processed using SMARTPLS 4.0, was used in data analysis to simultaneously test causal relationships between variables, primarily because the data was non-normal and the sample size was relatively small. The research instrument used was a questionnaire with a Likert scale of 1 to 5, which was used to measure the indicators of the four main variables: digital technology and human resource competency, transportation mode, and sustainable supply chain distribution. Validity and reliability tests were conducted first, with the conditions that the outer loading value is greater than 0.7, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is greater than 0.5, and the composite reliability is above 0.7 as indicators of adequate instrument quality.

Figure 4. 2 PLS Model

4.1 Measurement (Outer) Model Evaluation Results

Based on the data, the external load values for each indicator are higher than 0.7. This indicates that each variable meets the criteria for convergent validity and its indicators can be explained. The findings of the convergent validity test can also be confirmed using the average variance extracted (AVE) value in addition to

the external loading value. A successful measurement model is indicated by an AVE value greater than 0.5 for each latent concept:

Table 4.1: Transformation Methods

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Human Resource Competencies	0,843	0,847	0,888	0,615
Transportation Mode	0,877	0,889	0,911	0,675
Sustainable Supply Chain	0,865	0,865	0,908	0,712
Digital Technology	0,869	0,887	0,910	0,718

4.2.1 Reliability Test

All constructs were considered reliable because they had composite reliability values between 0.6 and 0.7 and Cronbach's

alpha values of more than 0.7 (Sarstedt et al., 2011).

4.2.2 Model Fit Test

Table 2 below displays the R² values

Table 4.2. Model Fit Test

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Transportation Mode	0,587	0,574
Sustainable Supply Chain	0,622	0,614

According to Table 2, the long R-Square value of the endogenous variable of Transportation Mode is 0.587, which indicates the strength of the variables of digital technology and HR competency in predicting Transportation Mode is 58.7%. The long R-Square value of the endogenous variable of Sustainable Supply Chain is 0.622, which indicates the strength of the variables of digital technology, HR competency and Transportation Mode in predicting Sustainable Supply Chain is 62.2%.

4.2.3 Hypothesis Testing Analysis

The results of the Path Coefficient direct effect test are as follows.

Table 4.3 Results of Hypothesis Testing through Path Coefficient direct effect Bootstrapping Technique

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Human Resources Competence -> Transportation Mode	0,120	0,104	0,109	1,104	0,270
Human Resources Competence -> Sustainable Supply Chain	0,705	0,708	0,082	8,637	0,000
Sustainable Supply Chain -> Mode of Transport	0,454	0,469	0,133	3,410	0,001
Digital Technology -> Mode of Transportation	0,284	0,283	0,128	2,211	0,027
Digital Technology -> Sustainable Supply Chain	0,115	0,113	0,105	1,096	0,273

1. The influence of digital technology on transportation modes in logistics services at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero).

Digital technology did not significantly impact transportation mode, with a coefficient of 0.284 and p = 0.027. This indicates that, in the context of PT Pos Indonesia, the use of digital technology has not yet fully and directly impacted the optimization of transportation mode selection. This could be due to a lack of integration of digital systems with transportation mode decision-making or a lack of training on the new digital system.

2. The Influence of Human Resources Competence on Transportation Modes in Logistics Services at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero).

With a coefficient of 0.120 and a p-value of 0.270, the influence of human resource competency on transportation modes is positive and significant. This indicates that the higher the human resource competency, the more optimal the selection and management of transportation modes in PT Pos Indonesia (Persero)'s logistics operations. Good human resource competency includes technical skills, an

understanding of logistics systems, and adaptability to technology, all of which contribute to operational effectiveness (Gunasekaran et al., 2017). Thus, developing human resource competency is a key factor in supporting the transformation of more efficient and responsive transportation modes.

3. The influence of digital technology on sustainable supply chain distribution at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero).

Digital technology has a positive and significant impact on sustainable supply chain distribution, with a coefficient of 0.115 and p = 0.273. This indicates that the implementation of digital technologies, such as real-time tracking systems, big data, and IoT, plays a crucial role in improving efficiency, transparency, and sustainability in distribution. Digital technology helps companies respond to changing market demands, minimize errors, and reduce logistics waste (Westerman et al., 2011; Christopher, 2016).

4. The Influence of HR Competence on Sustainable Supply Chain Distribution at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero).

Human resource competency also has a positive and significant impact on sustainable supply chain distribution, with a coefficient of 0.705 and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that employee competency directly impacts the success of efficient, adaptive, and environmentally friendly distribution. Skilled human resources are able to manage logistics systems holistically and sustainably, including data-driven decision-making and resource optimization.

5. The influence of a sustainable supply chain on the distribution of transportation modes at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero).

The influence of transportation mode on sustainable supply chain distribution is also statistically significant, with a coefficient of 0.454 and $p = 0.001$. These results indicate that selecting the right and efficient transportation mode can support the creation of an environmentally friendly and sustainable distribution system, for example through reduced emissions, low energy use, and fuel efficiency.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the results of the research analysis, it can be concluded that digital technology and human resource competency have different contributions to sustainable transportation and supply chain distribution modes at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero). Human resource competency is proven to have a positive and significant influence both directly on transportation and sustainable supply chain distribution modes. Transportation modes also act as a significant mediating variable in bridging the influence of human resource competency on supply chain distribution. Conversely, digital technology has a positive and significant influence only directly on sustainable supply chain distribution, but does not show a significant influence on transportation modes or indirectly through transportation modes. These findings indicate that strengthening human resource competency should be a top priority in improving the company's transportation and distribution performance, while the integration of digital technology in the transportation system still needs to be optimized so that its benefits can be felt comprehensively in supporting efficient and sustainable logistics distribution.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the research findings, it is recommended that **PT Pos Indonesia (Persero)** prioritize strengthening human resource competency as a strategic step to improve transportation effectiveness and sustainable supply chain distribution performance. Continuous training, professional certification, and the development of digital and green logistics skills are essential to ensure employees can optimally manage transportation operations and distribution processes. Given that transportation modes significantly mediate the relationship between human resource competency and supply chain distribution, the company should also enhance route planning, fleet management efficiency, and environmentally friendly transportation practices. Furthermore, although digital technology has shown a significant direct impact on sustainable supply chain distribution, its integration within transportation operations remains suboptimal; therefore, PT Pos Indonesia (Persero) needs to improve system integration, real-time tracking, and data-driven decision-making to maximize the benefits of digital transformation. Strengthening the synergy between competent human resources, optimized transportation systems, and integrated digital technology will support more efficient, competitive, and sustainable logistics distribution performance in the long term.

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